

MY PRECIOUS 100-YEAR-OLD TIBETAN TURQUOISE BEAD: A GIFT FROM MY GREAT-GRANDMOTHER

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ABSTRACT

I describe a turquoise bead purchased in about 1920 from a Muslim peddler and given to me in 1983 by my great-grandmother (Bde mtsho, 1904-1986) on the occasion of my third birthday. I also describe similar jewelry and their value to local herders in Yag mo (Yehemao) Village, Rkang tsha (Gangcha) County, Mtsho byang (Haibei) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China.

KEYWORDS

Tibetan hair-cutting ritual, Tibetan turquoise, Tibetan ornaments, protective amulets

MY LIFE, MY TURQUOISE

In 1981, I was born in a black yak-hair tent in Yag mo (Yehemao) Village, Rkang tsha (Gangcha) County, Mtsho byang Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. My maternal great-grandmother (Bde mtsho, 1904-1986) and my father (Dpal bzang, 1944-1992), who was a doctor, assisted my mother ('Ja' bho, b. 1944) at my birth.

I have two sisters (Lha kho, b. 1969, Klu mo tshe ring, b. 1977) and one brother ('Jigs gril rdo rje, b. 1972).

In 2006 when I was twenty-five-years old, Mother told me that my maternal great-grandmother had given me a turquoise bead during the Lo sar 'Tibetan New Year' period, the day that my third birthday was celebrated. *Ne'u ston* 'hair-cutting rituals for children' are held in my home community when a child observes their third Lo sar. Only a single braid was left when my hair was cut the first time. The turquoise bead was threaded onto a string and braided into my hair. My great-grandmother wished me an auspicious future of a long life, good health, and happiness with this gift.

FIG 1. In 1984, my great-grandmother gave me this turquoise bead.

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Mother and Lha kho said the turquoise bead was probably bought from a Muslim peddler more than one hundred years ago. Mother kept this turquoise for me until I married in 2010.

I am the only child in my family that married someone far from my home. My three siblings each brought a spouse to live in our home.

Mother gave me the turquoise bead as a symbol of the excellent relationship between my family and me. I greatly value this turquoise. It reminds me of who I am, where I am from, and our traditions and values. For these reasons, I have never considered selling it and never will. Not only is it an ornament, it also gives me spiritual support, protects me, and brings me good luck. I treasure it and keep it carefully.

Now I have a son (Kun dga' nor bu, b. 2012) who is my only child. If I have a daughter, I will give it to her at some point, or maybe I will give it to my future daughter-in-law, or perhaps to my son.

In 2018, I was shopping in Chab cha (Qiabuqia) Township for Tibetan-style jewelry and Tibetan robes. When I entered one shop, a shopkeeper noticed my turquoise, approached me, and asked how long I had had it and if I was willing to sell it. While replying that the turquoise was very important to me, I chose not to divulge its history.

Beads are usually considered ornaments for women - decorations for women, enhancing their beauty. Necklaces also can be seen as important symbols of value and a family's wealth. If a woman has many beads, her family is considered rich and of high social status. Two to three decades ago, the more necklaces you wore, the richer you were considered to be.

Nowadays, those ideas have changed due to rapid social changes and because more people have attended official schools. Many people think the simpler, the better, so wearing just one or two necklaces is considered appropriate. If a woman wears too many beads, some may ridicule her.

Many years ago, the materials for necklaces included authentic gems. There were few artificial or fake ones. Nowadays, many beads are made of synthetic materials that even, in some cases, may be detrimental to the health of the wearer. Nevertheless, some try to sell these as authentic for high prices.

Beads have also changed over the years. They were originally made by hand or by using simple machines. The shape of the beads was typically round or triangular. But in recent years, technology has been employed to create various shapes and styles.

In my home in Rkang tsha, mothers pass their beads to their daughters as dowries or traditional family gifts to their daughters-in-law. If there are several daughters, which is the case in my family (there are three), the necklaces are usually divided among them all. My oldest sister has more jewelry and ornaments in my family because she was the first to marry, and somehow the older one has more.

In a family, the wife has genuine ownership of the necklaces. In my home area, the local custom is that women usually wear necklaces and are the jewelry keepers.

My aunt has many valuable necklaces of *gzi* 'agate', and other beads. When my oldest sister was about six-years-old, she would go to my paternal aunt's home to play. Later, when my sister said she liked my aunt's beads, my aunt immediately let her choose one. My aunt's husband and other family members did not care if she gave a bead to others. Years later, we identified the piece she had chosen as a *gzi*, a costly ornament. My aunt had the power and authority at that time to do whatever she wanted with her ornaments and necklaces. She could exchange them with others or give them to others as she liked.

There are many beliefs that a necklace is a "condensed" valuable object, functioning as insurance in case misfortune befalls the owner or even a whole family. My mother said there is a saying that if there is one valuable necklace in the village or valley, it can protect all the villagers or even the people in the valley.

My oldest sister experienced this protection. In about 2003, she suffered from various illnesses, went to several hospitals, and had about five operations. She believes a *gzi* can draw poison. When she had her operations, the *gzi* lost brightness, and the white stripes became black because, my sister explained, of the surgical anesthetic. After the surgeries, when she had recovered, the *gzi* returned to its original black and white stripes and regained its brightness. My sister believed that the *gzi* protects her like an amulet.

I find it challenging to distinguish imitation beads from genuine ones. Even though they cannot explain to me very clearly, my mother and my oldest sister maintain that they can identify genuine beads based on holding and touching them (the authentic beads are heavier), biting (real beads are hard as stone), bright and authentic colors, and a special brightness in direct sunshine.

Apart from their quality and the materials, another difference between new and old necklaces is their value. Old beads are generally regarded as more valuable because the materials used are typically real, the workmanship is considered superior, and the old beads symbolize one's identity and cultural values. Today, anyone can purchase inexpensive imitation beads and necklaces, which is why they have lost their special meaning.

In summary, the old beads are more important because they have exceptional meanings that cannot be purchased for an ethnic group, a community, a family, between mothers and daughters, and special meanings between generations. An old necklace is a symbol of tradition and family bonds. Passing it from generation to generation communicates a precious relationship in that family and in that community. My bead is also special and precious, bringing me luck and happiness. In my heart, this turquoise is priceless.

FIGS 2 & 3. (L) I wear my turquoise at a Tibetan gathering and (R) at my home in Zi ling (Xining) City (2016, 2017; Pad ma gyal).

TIBETAN TERMS

'ja' bho འཇའ་བོ།

'jigs gril rdo rje འཇིགས་གྲིལ་རྡོ་རྗེ།

bde mtsho བདེ་མཚོ།

chab cha ཚབ་ཇ།

dpal bzang དཔལ་བཟང།

gzi གཟི།

klu mo tshe ring ལུ་མོ་ཚེ་རིང།

kun dga' nor bu ལུན་དགའ་ནོར་བུ།

lha kho ལྷ་ཁོ།

mgon thar skyid མགོན་ཐར་སྐྱིད།

ne'u ston རྟེན་སྲོམ།

mtsho byang མཚོ་བྱང།

mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྐྱོན།

pad ma gyal པདྨ་རྒྱལ།

rkang tsha རྟང་ཚ།

yag mo ཡག་མོ།

zi ling ཟི་ལིང།

CHINESE TERMS

Gangcha 刚察

Gongtaijie 贡太杰

Haibei 海北

Qiabuqia 恰卜恰

Qinghai 青海

Xining 西宁

Yehamao 冶合茂